

ICARUS will be the driver for a new start of the **European PV industry**. ICARUS aims at turning the upstream process wastes, rich in highly pure Si and energy-dense, into a secondary raw material.

It will demonstrate modular processing solutions at industrial scale to retrieve 95% of high-value raw materials from silicon ingot and wafer manufacturing, through eco-efficient processing, refining, and transformation of industrial silicon, graphite and silica waste streams.

Three industrial pilots producing silicon, silica and graphite raw materials:

Pretreated and purified silicon, silica and graphite raw materials

Pyrometallurgical process using recycled silicon, silica and graphite for high purity silicon

Granular silicon feedstock for photovoltaic applications

Coordinator: SINTEF

Project leader: [Martin Bellmann](#)

<https://www.icarus.eu.com/>

One **industrial pilot** converting silicon waste into full value industrial commodities: green hydrogen, silica and silicates.

Different high-end product applications with strict raw material quality standards, to assess the technical and economic viability of different applications: Si-photovoltaics, Al-Si alloys, thermoelectric modules and generators, lithium-ion battery cells, silicon carbide powders and fine-grained graphite